

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

Call: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-02

Project 101075572 — MARINEWIND

T1.3_Italian Lab 2nd Co-creation Workshop Report

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Document history

Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
21/03/2024	V1	First draft by APRE
28/03/2024		Final draft by APRE

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: *Port System Authority of the Central Northern Tyrrhenian Sea – Vespucci Dock, Civitavecchia (Rome, Italy)*

EVENT DATE: *March, the 15th, 2024 (9-13 a.m. CET, 4')*

EVENT TITLE: *“Lo sviluppo consapevole dell’eolico offshore galleggiante: falsi miti ed impatti” / “A responsible development for the floating offshore wind technology: false myths and impacts”*

TYPE OF EVENT: *Physical*

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: *Co-creation Workshop*

EVENT AFFILIATION: *N/A*

LEAD ORGANISER: *APRE – Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea (Agency for the Promotion of the European Research)*

CO-ORGANISERS: *RSE – Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico; RSE – Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (Research on the Energy System); the Institute of Marine Engineering (INM) of the CNR – Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (National Research Council)*

LANGUAGE: *Italian*

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The workshop, which is a follow-up of the previous European Maritime Day event hosted by the Port Authority of Bari in June 2023, focused specifically on the state of the art of Off-shore Wind Farms in the Lazio Region, and, with a wider perspective, on the Marine Spatial Planning for the Mediterranean Sea.

Besides the involvement of APRE as the Coordinator of the MARINEWIND project, the Italian event was co-hosted by prominent Italian research centres and fellow MARINEWIND partners, i.e. CNR and RSE, who are currently involved in innovative technological projects for the energy transition.

The discussion mainly stressed on the perceived uncertainty regarding the regulatory framework both at the national and at the regional level, as well as on the impact of FOWTs on the local economy (including fishing, tourism and small and medium enterprises activities) and on the environment, analysing and dispelling many false myths and misconceptions that are currently tackling a wider social acceptance for the technology.

To this end, fishermen's associations and prominent players in the sector industry were involved in a direct debate not only with the technical experts of the MARINEWIND consortium, but also with representatives of the Directorate for Blue Economy of the Lazio Region.

OBJECTIVES

Inspired by the specific objectives of the MARINEWIND project, the workshop aimed at:

- Increasing awareness on FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.
- Encouraging social acceptance by directly involving local communities and local fishermen and by addressing any environmental issues.

- Facilitating communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and indirectly involved in Italian MARINEWIND Lab.

TARGET AUDIENCE

Following the Quintuple Helix approach, the event targeted representatives of public authorities, civil society, green innovators, academia and industry directly involved in the Italian Lab. For each specific category, the involved actors were:

- **Industry:** FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, tech/project developers, trade associations (fisheries and tourism).
- **Academia:** Scientific & Research Community.
- **Public authorities:** at European (EC, European associations, e.g., ICLEI, ERRIN), national (Ministries for Energy, for Industry and Environment) and local level (Regional authorities), maritime transport authorities, policymakers.
- **Civil society:** NGOs, civil society organisations, and citizens.
- **Green innovation:** SMEs, public/private financial investors, insurers, ecologists, environmental organisations, and natural parks.

Additionally, through dissemination activities and synergies, the event targeted actors and beneficiaries of other EU funded projects and initiatives (e.g., the HE project FLOATFARM).

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: 31 participants

Figure 1 - Participants overview

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

2.1 Off-shore wind farm projects and marine spatial planning: focus on the Lazio Region

MARINEWIND project partner RSE – Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (Energy System Research) has presented the audience an overview of the current situation for the Lazio Region regarding the quantity and characteristics of the pending request for Offshore Wind Farms, and the Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP). All data presented comes from the Italian Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security and is updated as of December 31, 2023. The following elements emerged from the presentation:

- An overview of the situation of requests for authorisation for Offshore Wind Farms in Italy has highlighted how in some areas there is a high density of projects. Furthermore, the only projects with fixed technology are those located in the Emilia Romagna Region. It was highlighted that, regarding four projects, the plant is located off the coast of one region but the connection to the grid takes place in another region, creating a potential critical factor.
- Moving specifically to the authorisation requests in the Lazio Region, it was mentioned that the type of wind turbine proposed in the majority of the projects presented (5 cases out of 8) is the 15 MW Vestas V236, with a rotor diameter of 236 m and a hub height of approximately 150 m.
- Focusing on Civitavecchia, the site chosen for the workshop, regarding the MSP, it emerged that six Offshore Wind Farm projects were presented in the provinces of Viterbo and Rome. All the projects are located in areas with energy as a priority use, or general use areas, although for two projects some wind turbines fall in areas with other uses (fishing, maritime transport and ports, environmental protection and natural resources). Some projects appear to be partially overlapping.¹
- With regard to factors such as bathymetry, producibility and distance from the coast, it was highlighted that all the projects are located in areas with seabed depths of less than 500 m (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/bathymetry>) and with producibility at 150 m above sea level. between 2500 and 3500 MWh/MW (<https://atlanteoelico.rse-web.it/>). Furthermore, all the projects are located within 12 nautical miles from the coast (the territorial water limit), although for two projects some wind turbines are located slightly beyond this limit.
- Still regarding the MSP situation in Lazio, four Offshore Wind Farm projects were presented in the area off the coast of the city of Olbia, two of which are expected to be connected in Lazio. The two projects are located in areas with priority uses i.e. fishing, maritime transport and ports, environmental protection and natural resources. A project is partly overlapped with another.
- Of the aforementioned projects off the coast of Olbia, the former is located in areas with bathymetry between 500 and 1000 m, while the latter in areas with seabed deeper than 1000 m (<https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/bathymetry>). Both projects are located in areas with producibility at 150 m above sea level exceeding 3500 MWh/MW

¹ Less than a fortnight after the workshop, the Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security communicated the admissibility of the EIA (Environmental Impact Assessment) request, presented 2 years ago now, for the offshore wind project off the coast of Civitavecchia.

(<https://atlanteolico.rse-web.it/>), and are planned to be built at 12 nautical miles from the coast (the territorial water limit).

- Regarding the situation outlined by the Italian regulatory framework, the Legislative Decree 199/2021 - Transposition of the European Directive 2018/2001 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (so-called RED II), lists, in article 23, the authorisation procedures relating to off-shore plants and the identification of suitable areas.
- The authorisation is issued by the Ministry of the Environment and Energy Security (MASE), in agreement with the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport (MIT), and after consulting the Ministry of Agriculture, Food Sovereignty and Forestry (MASAF). This authorization also includes works for connection to the network, with a single procedure including the release of the concession for use of state maritime property (amendment to art. 12 of LEGISLATIVE DECREE 29 December 2003, no. 387).
- As part of the identification of areas suitable for the installation of offshore renewable energy production plants, the areas identified for the production of renewable energy by the Maritime Space Management Plan are considered valid.
- In suitable areas and in areas not subject to restrictions incompatible with the establishment of off-shore plants, the competent Landscape Authority expresses itself with a non-binding mandatory opinion, identifying, where necessary, specific requirements aimed at better insertion into the landscape and protection of assets of archaeological interest.
- Still with regard to the national regulatory framework, it must be considered that the European Directive 2014/89 provided for the drafting by member states of Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) by 2021. However, the Italian plan, made available in draft in August 2022 with the start of the Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) procedure, is still in this phase, and consequently not yet adopted.
- Considering the Law 9 December 2023, n. 181 (so-called “Energy Safety Decree”), the Article 8, relating to measures for the development of the supply chain relating to floating wind farms at sea, provides that, within thirty days from the date of entry into force of the conversion law, the MASE will publish a notice aimed at acquiring expressions of interest for the identification, in at least two ports in central-southern Italy, or in port areas adjacent to areas in which the gradual elimination of the use of coal is underway, of maritime state-owned areas for the floating offshore wind supply chain. Furthermore, in this law, the MASE adopts and publishes a handbook relating to the obligations and information necessary for the start of the single procedure for the authorisation of floating wind farms (art. 23 paragraph 6 of 199/2021).
- Another relevant data is the fact that, despite a potential of over 200 GW, the proposal for the National Integrated Plan for Energy and Climate (PNIEC) in Italy foresees only 2.1 GW of offshore wind by 2030.

2.2 The environmental impacts of offshore wind power

MARINEWIND project partner INM-CNR – the Institute of Marine Engineering of the Italian National Research Council has presented the audience an overview of the environmental impacts of the

offshore wind power², starting from how FOWTs are positioned regarding the so-called “Good Environmental Status”. As a reference, the European Commission’s Maritime Strategy Framework Directive defines the Good Environmental Status (GES) as “The environmental status of marine waters where these provide ecologically diverse and dynamic oceans and seas which are clean, healthy and productive”. The following elements emerged from the presentation:

- Regarding the state of the art in terms of knowledge of environmental impacts, it was highlighted that the data coming from monitoring campaigns are still limited and incomplete, and that the analyses lack of an interdisciplinary approach. In general, in fact, the analyses take place at a local, rather than global, level, as well as covering basins with different characteristics compared to the Mediterranean (such as the North Seas), as well as different construction technologies (bottom fixed instead of floating). Furthermore, the forecasts are also based on experience acquired in other sectors and on mathematical models with different degrees of accuracy. Therefore, current knowledge gaps on the marine environment make quantitative assessment of the effects of FOWTs difficult.
- The first environmental impact highlighted was the alteration of wind speed and changes in the dynamics of the atmosphere and seas. Wind farms create wake effects that reduce wind speed and energy downstream, with a local impact on climate, ocean dynamics (local wave field variation, vertical mixing, seasonal stratification) with possible cascading effects on distribution of biomass and sedimentary processes. Despite uncertainty between modelled and observed effects, studies suggest minimal climate impacts and small reductions in atmospheric energy. Although the concerns about the ocean dynamics remain, the data suggest limited disturbance.
- When the analyses talk about the risk of accidents, it is important to underline that they are referring to a risk associated not only with accidents directly related to the Wind Farms (e.g., accidents to wind turbines, including fires, wind turbines falling into the sea and collisions with ships), but also with natural hazards, such as storms and other extreme events.
- Regarding the impact on birds, there are two main effects: 1) mortality due to direct collisions and 2) movement of birds from the areas where they obtain food. Nevertheless, experimental tests for offshore installations are lacking, although some specific studies are underway.
- Another element of risk is represented by moorings and underwater cables, which could cause collisions and entrapment of marine mammals.
- As for the underwater noise pollution, it could impact on fish, marine mammals and cetaceans during the installation, operational and decommissioning phases of the Farms.
- Variations in the electromagnetic fields of electric cables, during the operational phase, have a negative impact on specific fish that use electromagnetic signals to locate prey. Furthermore, they interfere with their ability to orient themselves in relation to geomagnetic fields, potentially changing their migration patterns.

² Farr et al. *Potential environmental effects of deepwater floating offshore wind energy facilities Ocean and Coastal Management* 207, 2021

- Another element being analysed as potentially harmful to the environment is the alteration of the habitat for communities of benthic and pelagic fish and invertebrates: mooring lines and floating substructures also attract alien species due to the introduction of artificial substrates and could, therefore, have a negative impact on biodiversity. Despite concerns about the proliferation of non-native species, studies have not yet demonstrated significant deleterious effects on reef fish or benthic communities.
- Regarding the integrity of the seabed, it has been pointed out how it can be affected by the fact that floating platforms require mooring and anchoring systems, which can consist of heavy chains to keep their substructures in place and, in some cases, the use of drag anchors.
- Measures to prevent biofouling and corrosion of both the platform and the catenaries can introduce toxins on a local scale, affecting water quality: however, the adoption of ecological alternatives can reduce the risk that water deterioration represents for marine species.
- Other impacts highlighted are:
 - The decommissioning, that includes local impacts on the marine environment (destruction of the habitat created around the infrastructure, noise, release of chemicals and materials in general, increase in water turbidity), but also global (disposal of non-recyclable materials).
 - The construction of new support infrastructure in coastal areas, that creates impacts at the local level.
 - The presence of critical materials in the permanent magnets poses environmental problems due to their massive extraction (as well as concerns on future availability and political problems).
 - Cumulative impacts: it is important to be able to evaluate at a regional level the effect of multiple installations and the one combined with other human activities. The global impact will be quite different, once all the planned wind power is installed.
 - The lack of biodiversity sensors, that represents a common gap in knowledge of the sea.
- The analysis presented by the CNR also covered the positive impacts of FOWTs on the environment, namely:
 - The creation of an artificial reef: mooring anchors and underwater cables can act as artificial coral reefs, attracting marine life and serving as valuable tools of conservation. These "barrier effects" could increase the abundance of local species, create marine refuges and generate spillover effects, increasing biodiversity.
 - The emergence of new marine protected areas (with effects on the fish fauna reserve): the reduction or absence of fishing around offshore wind farms creates reserves for the species. The resulting proliferation is characterised by a greater concentration of marine species and their predators (birds, marine mammals, fish). Furthermore, increasing marine biomass and biodiversity has a positive effect on the seabed.
- As regards the specificity of the Mediterranean Sea compared to other basins covered by the aforementioned analyses, both the lack of knowledge of deep marine habitats and the large number of marine protected areas were highlighted.

- The Mediterranean Sea is not only a biodiversity hot-spot, but also has the highest number of endangered species and fragile habitats due to factors like climate change, the large number of activities happening on the sea, the depletion of resources and pollution.

2.3 Social acceptance perspective: myths and misconceptions about FOWTs

The Consultancy Company The European House – Ambrosetti presented an overview of the ten most common and widespread false myths and misconceptions tackling the social acceptance of FOWTs, providing a series of data and arguments, coming from the analysis of the "Floating Offshore Wind Community" observatory, that refute each of those prejudices in its Strategic Report. In fact, the mission of the Floating Offshore Wind Community³ is to fuel a conscious debate around the benefits and industrial implications that Italy can reap through the construction of floating offshore wind farms, and the creation of an industrial leadership in this new frontier of technologies for renewable energy. Among the aforementioned ten false myths concerning FOWTs, these are the most significant:

- False myth 1 – To accelerate the decarbonisation process, it is necessary to identify a single green technology to focus on: instead, the synergistic and complementary contribution of all available green technologies, including floating offshore wind, must be exploited to achieve climate neutrality objectives. In fact, the floating offshore wind will be an important part of the Italian energy mix by 2050, with at least 20 GW.
- False myth 2 – the Mediterranean Sea is not suitable to host offshore turbines, which damage the coast and the marine ecosystem: on the contrary, considering the morphological characteristics of the Mediterranean Sea and the depth of its waters, as well as the distinctive characteristics of floating offshore wind power, this technology represents the most suitable solution to scale the installed capacity of renewable energy sources with the least impact on the environment, also considering that Offshore Wind Farms are almost invisible on the horizon line.
- False myth 3 – In Italy, it makes no sense to focus on floating offshore wind technology because there is no development potential: on the contrary, Italy is the ideal country for floating offshore wind power, being the third potential market in the world. In fact, more than 60% of the Italian renewable electricity potential comes from this technology.
- False myth 4 - The best strategy for Italy is to wait for other countries to develop floating offshore wind power before starting its own development cycle: instead, in third countries, the strategies for adopting floating offshore wind power have already been started and consolidated. Therefore, whoever manages to achieve the industrial development of this technology first will become the supplier to all other markets.
- False myth 5 – The Italian supply chain is not ready to start working on ambitious floating offshore wind targets for 2030 and 2040: on the contrary, if the government set short, medium and long-term objectives, providing a stimulus to investors, and establishes a clear

³ The documents produced up to date by the Floating Offshore Wind Community can be consulted here: <https://www.ambrosetti.eu/news/il-contributodelleolico-offshore-galleggiante-perladecarbonizzazione-dellitalia/>

industrial vision for this technology, Italy can aspire to more than the current 2.1 GW by 2030, leveraging an industrial value chain in which Italy has leadership, for a value of 255 billion euros and 1.3 million employed.

- False myth 6 - The development of renewable energy sources does not allow the creation of value directly in local territories and benefits foreign supply chains: on the contrary, the floating offshore wind sector generates high positive externalities in local territories, involving not only large manufacturing companies, but also national and local SMEs.
- False myth 7 - Italy cannot start floating offshore wind projects if the MSP is not completed first: on the contrary, best practices at European level show that in the short term it is possible to follow a decentralised approach for the rapid identification of offshore wind farm sites suitable for the development of large projects, while implementing MSP based on a centralised mechanism. The prominent example on the matter is the case study of Ireland.
- False myth 8 - In Italy, it is not possible to overcome local oppositions and avoid NIMBY movements (Not In My Back Yard), which obstacle the installation of floating offshore wind turbines: on the contrary, several best practices at European level show that there are concertation mechanisms that make stakeholder participation possible already in the definition phase of offshore wind projects, increasing their social acceptability in less than a year.
- False myth 9 - The Levelized Cost Of Electricity (LCOE) associated with floating offshore wind represents a huge obstacle to the sustainable development of this technology: instead, the standardisation and subsequent industrialisation of the technology will allow, as has happened for fixed-bottom offshore wind, a significant reduction of costs.
- False myth 10 - There is no adequate electricity network infrastructure to develop floating offshore wind projects in Italy: on the contrary, even if further adjustments of the Italian electricity grid are necessary, the Development Plan by TERNA (the largest independent operator of electricity transmission networks in Europe) already includes the strengthening of its export capacity by 2030.

2.4 Focus on the HE FLOATFARM project

MARINEWIND partner CNR is also a consortium member for the fellow 3-year Horizon Europe project “FLOATFARM - Developing the Next Generation of Environmentally-Friendly Floating Wind Farms with Innovative Technologies and Sustainable Solutions”, started on January the 1st, 2024, and coordinated by the Technical University of Berlin. Considering how relevant the topic is for MARINEWIND analysis, synergies among these two projects are currently being explored by the respective consortia. Therefore, an overview of the FLOATFARM project has been provided to the audience during the workshop.

FLOATFARM aims at significantly advancing the maturity and competitiveness of floating offshore wind (FOW) technology by increasing energy production, achieving significant cost reductions within the design and implementation phases, improving offshore wind value chain and supporting EU companies in this growing sector. Ultimately, FLOATFARM is working to decrease negative environmental impacts on marine life and to enhance the public acceptability of FOW, thereby

accelerating the EU energy transition.

To this end, a number of critical technologies have been identified as key catalysts. They apply to different conceptual scales, from individual floating offshore wind turbine level (Action 1) to farm level (Action 2) and environmental and socio-economic perspectives (Action 3). The project is proposing innovations for: 1) ROTOR TECHNOLOGY, where innovative rotor designs for improved energy capture will be explored in a co-design approach with innovative control techniques, improved floaters, and a groundbreaking generator concept; 2) MOORING AND ANCHORING, where shared mooring and innovative dynamic cabling will be investigated; 3) WIND FARM CONTROL, where novel control strategies will be exploited to increase the farm power density, and 4) ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT MITIGATION, where marine noise emissions and impacts on marine species of FOW farms will be addressed, innovative artificial reefs will be pioneered and social acceptance will be studied.

To ensure that effective solutions are pursued and TRL5 can be achieved, FLOATFARM is adopting a holistic approach that combines innovative designs, experimental demonstration at laboratory scale, modelling with a suite of beyond state-of-the-art numerical tools, and demonstration in a unique open-sea laboratory, where a new 1:7 scale 15MW FOWT will be tested in combination with novel floaters, moorings and controls, ensuring systematic assessment and validation that are thus far unprecedented in FOWT research.

2.5 The impact of FOWTs on local economic activities: the perspective of fishermen's associations

The impact of offshore wind on economic activities, particularly on fishing, was analysed by the intervention of the Consorzio Mediterraneo s.c.a.r.l. Established in 1996, the Mediterranean Consortium brings together fifteen fishing cooperatives located throughout the country and a national coordination centre. The Consortium constitutes the technical-scientific reference structure for Lega Pesca – Italian National Association of Fishing Cooperatives. The Mediterranean Consortium operates directly or through its associates to contribute to the expansion and dissemination of knowledge and the in-depth study of the main problems in the fishing sector, with particular reference to the biological, ecological, technological, economic and educational aspects with the objective of promoting the development and valorisation of fishing, the fishing economy, aquaculture and the protection of the coastal strip in Italy.

Below, the main elements that emerged from the intervention:

- Complete data on the economic impact of FOWT is currently missing.
- Italy has a fleet of 14,000 professional boats mainly focused on trawling with depths from 50 to 8-900 metres.
- There are problems of dialogue and exchange of data between different competent bodies (it happens that both potential offshore wind projects and potential projects for the development of mariculture are foreseen in the same area).
- New transit routes must be identified, the areas under concession for wind power could sometimes be circumnavigated.

- It is necessary to understand whether small-scale fishing and some types of aquaculture are compatible with floating systems, for now fishing associations start from the assumption that they are not.
- In some areas of the Mediterranean Sea, especially in western Sardinia, the installation of offshore wind farms is planned in areas such that the farms would almost completely block areas heavily exploited by trawling, with repercussions on the displacement of fishing activities in other areas with more concentration and a possible crisis in the sector. Overall, in the Mediterranean, it is estimated that FOWTs would cause a 43% reduction in fishing areas.
- The Consortium could not provide specific data on the Lazio Region, as it analysed the most significant areas for their members.

2.6 The perspective of the regional authority: building a blue future for the Lazio Region

The specific intervention of the representatives of the Blue Economy Area of the Directorate for Economic Development of the Lazio Region was anticipated by the discussion that arose spontaneously among the workshop participants. The salient points of the intervention, however, were the four areas of strategic intervention for the Region:

1. The Maritime space planning, which provides, for example, a priority use for wind power in the Civitavecchia area;
2. The Regional Law n.2 of 02/24/2022 “Provision for the promotion of training, employment and development in the Blue Economy sectors”: Lazio is the first Region to adopt it;
3. The Regional PUA (Plan for the Use of State Maritime Property Areas) and Municipal PUA;
4. The Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3), with focus on the Maritime Economy as a smart area of specialisation for the Region.

Furthermore, it was highlighted how the Region actively participates, as Founding Member, in the BIG (Blue Italian Growth) Cluster through Lazio Innova, an in-house company of the Lazio Region (also owned, with a minority share, by the Chamber of Commerce of Rome) which represents the result of the process of reorganisation of the companies of the Lazio Region dedicated to innovation, credit and economic development. The BIG Cluster works to reach a shared framework among the main national stakeholders on the development trajectories to be considered priorities. The analysis of development trajectories focuses on the following vertical areas:

- Marine environment and coastal strip.
- Blue Biotechnologies.
- Renewable Energy from the sea.
- Marine abiotic resources.
- Marine biotic resources.
- Shipbuilding and Marine Robotics.

To these, in parallel, the following transversal themes are added:

- Research infrastructures.
- Sustainability and economic uses of the sea.

- Skills and jobs.

3 ROUNDTABLES TOPICS OVERVIEW

The roundtable discussion naturally began with questions and issues from the participants to the speakers after each intervention. The main points of debate, from which both critical issues emerged (which were discussed during the session) and real barriers (with which the project will have to deal with in its future activities and in the subsequent workshops, looking for possible solutions), but also incentives and enabling factors, were the following:

- In Italy, the Decree which identifies the areas suitable for the installation of energy production systems from renewable sources, in implementation of article 20, paragraphs 1 and 2, of Legislative Decree no. 199/2021, is in the process of being published. The Decree attributes to the Regions and Autonomous Provinces the responsibility of identifying in their territory the surfaces and areas suitable for the installation of energy systems from renewable sources with the aim of maximising their potential. The representative of the Blue Economy Area of the Directorate for Economic Development of the Lazio Region highlighted how, in her opinion, the aforementioned decree is fundamental for outlining the MSP of Lazio. However, RSE responded by stating that the suitable areas covered by the decree will only concern onshore wind energy plants: the Decree does not contain indications on offshore wind since planning and management are closely linked to Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP), which it is of national, and not regional, competence, although it provides for the involvement of the regions. The Region objected that, although energy is not a matter of concurrent legislative competence between the Italian State and the Regions, other matters which concern offshore wind farms are, therefore the Regions have autonomy in defining the areas linked to the MSP, although they are currently in a phase of regulatory development and, in fact, stuck in an impasse.
- The point of view of the Industry, specifically of those directly responsible for the design of some offshore wind plants in Italy, has communicated great apprehension on the part of the sector, because in their opinion the MSP issue is not addressed in a competent manner. The first problem concerns the Regions' intervention in the matter: the Regions, according to the industrial sector, have not understood that their maritime spatial planning cannot go beyond the limit of 12 miles. The representatives of the Region objected that, given what was said above on the Suitable Areas Decree and on the matters of concurrent legislative competence of the Regions which enter into the merits of offshore wind farms (although energy is the exclusive competence of the Italian State), they could be called, in the future, to identify dedicated areas in the MSP even beyond the 12 miles threshold.
- The aforementioned Offshore Wind Farms planners involved in the workshop replied that the Region can only have jurisdiction with regard to the passage trajectories, always within 12 miles from the coast, to bring the electric cables to the Farms. In this regard, the industry expects a collaborative approach from the Regions, because, if the latter decide to act against environmental and economic common sense, they could complicate the situation, forcing the industry to contemplate convoluted trajectories for electrical cables, slowing down the process and greatly increasing production costs.

- The industry's point of view has highlighted that it is not enough to identify areas for wind farms taking into exclusive consideration the wind: geological parameters should also be taken into account.
- As things currently stand, only 17% of the Italian seabed has been investigated, therefore only a small part and generally close to the coasts, nothing offshore, where the Offshore Wind Farms should be located. Bringing the analysis of seabed for floating offshore to an adequate level would require funding in the order of billions of euros, so it is unlikely that the investigation will actually be addressed: for this reason, the geotechnical suitability of the seabed for anchoring should not be a prerequisite for the granting of authorisations for offshore wind farms.
- In 2022, each Italian Region was called to specify the priority uses of its territory, both present and future: the representatives of the Lazio Region stated that they were the only region to have foreseen, at the time, an area for which wind power represented the priority use, but, in the aftermath, they have been blocked by the fact that they yet have to wait for validation by the national legislation with the MSP.
- The representatives of the Strategic Consultancy Company sector have highlighted how, in the Suitable Areas Decree, there are no indications regarding offshore wind. However, it should be noted that, in the first version of the decree, a 40% constraint was expressed on the power of offshore plants, while in the second version that the environment commission submitted to the Regions, the power level rose to 100%.
- Considering how the industry has highlighted problems at the centralised level for the MSP, the point of view of the Strategic Consulting for the sector is to work in synergy with the private technical developers, who have already carried out geophysical and geotechnical analyses. A significant best practice on the topic is the Irish one: in fact, the Irish Government, while still working on their national MSP, is favouring a decentralised parallel approach, working together with private technical developers, in order to shorten waiting times.
- The representatives of the Italian Association for Offshore Renewable Energy (AERO) highlighted how, due to the fact that the Ministry of Transport had not identified specific areas and bands suitable for the construction of offshore wind farm projects, the SEA Commission has had to carry out an incomplete analysis, without including offshore. As a consequence, the Ministry of Transport has now resumed its work on the matter, and, within a year, it is supposed to be able to propose the final scenario once again, this time taking into account the state of the art of the requests made on offshore wind energy. In the hypothesis that these requests do not fall within the suitable areas, the situation would open up a legal dispute with the Italian State. Most of the 83 projects advanced by private operators should, in fact, be within the 12 miles from the coast (concession of State maritime property - exemption n° 40).
- On the topic, according to the National Wind Energy Association (ANEV), in order to avoid a major dispute between the investments already made by the operators and the choices of the State, a safeguard clause is absolutely needed in the Suitable Areas Decree for the interventions already carried out (up to the request for a single authorisation procedure).
- The Lazio Region stated that, in Italy, the issue of offshore wind energy has been left out of

the MSP because the selection of suitable areas for this type of plant requires a long technical-scientific study, so the Country will follow suit of many other European countries, including Finland. In Finland, in fact, in order not to block the rest of the MSP, the choice was made to approve the planning within the established timescales without including the offshore. Finland, like Italy, has given itself a year to study the offshore issue. Another element to take into consideration, as already explained, is the fact that the waiting time for the publishing of the Suitable Areas Decrees blocked the process.

- In response to the analysis of the environmental impacts of FOWTs, and in particular on the integrity of the seabed, the wind farm designers present in the workshop highlighted how, already in the first floating project presented in Italy in 2019, they made a proposal for anchoring technologies that goes beyond the tradition of anchors that comes from oil platforms (i.e. anchors with chains that ensure stability but which, when moving, devastate the seabed). Therefore, the aforementioned impact is not relevant, according to their point of view, since the world of offshore wind has already discarded the hypothesis of chaining, orienting itself instead on fixed anchoring, a technology now consolidated in the sector.
- Regarding the concern about microclimate modification, the industry pointed out that the observations in the analyses were made over the North Sea: however, it is important to note that in the last five years only one case of fog park modification has been observed. Nevertheless, apart from considering that this impact was an extreme case also for the Northern Sea, the private experts have studied that, in the Mediterranean Sea, the temperatures are not as such as to create condensation and consequentially impacting on fog density.
- Concerning the modification of the wave flow, the industry related studies have proven that the pieces of the wind farms are crossed by the wave flow in an almost transparent way.
- The CNR's response to all these objections made by the Industrial sector on the relevance of the harmful impacts of FOWTs on the environment was that, to date, the expected potential of wind power is not yet realised, and that therefore the environmental analyses must take into consideration the risks that will occur when all the wind farms will be active in the Mediterranean Sea. In fact, the cumulative impact must be taken into account by all environmental analyses, including MARINEWIND's one.
- Regarding the impact of the life cycle of the materials of which the Offshore Wind Farms are composed, RSE has highlighted the possibility of recycling the blades at the end of their life, which has already been studied for some time: it would be desirable for Italy to follow, in this sense, the direction already taken by Spain, where, with Next Generation EU funds, they are opening six factories for the recycling of blades. In Spain, the currently installed onshore capacity is greater than in Italy, but they are already working in anticipation of future offshore plant installations.
- To this input, an Industry representative responded that in Europe they are already working on the use of a particular recyclable resin: nevertheless, RSE replied that this is not the case of Italy.
- The representatives of the industrial sector also highlighted how technology is also progressing in terms of moorings, going so far as to study the possibility of sharing mooring points, so as to optimise the effective anchoring points on the seabed and cause a lower

impact on the marine ecosystem.

- The Floating Offshore Wind Community proposed the following inputs regarding the policy framework and the objectives of the FOWT:
 - To define a clear long-term industrial vision with an ambitious objective for floating offshore wind, stimulating the development of dedicated supply chains.
 - To have an Italian MSP as soon as possible, since the Maritime Space Planning is fundamental to reassuring investors, planning infrastructures and avoiding conflicts.
 - To measure the incentives to the industrial opportunity and the social effects.
 - To have an alignment between the Italian government and the local institutions involved in complex projects such as the Offshore Wind Farms.
 - To promote the planning for advancing the grid in a synergistic way with the MSP.
- According to the regional representatives, the MSP will impact the autonomy of regional policies.
- The Lazio Region pointed out that their insertion of the Blue Economy Area in the Economic Development Directorate is a precise choice.
- The Port Authority of Civitavecchia, responsible for the procedures for the first floating offshore projects presented, highlighted how it is necessary to keep in mind the fact that the port area is a complex navigation space, with main traffic routes which are also transversal. Therefore, national and international regulations are necessary, in order to allow the eventual coexistence of future offshore wind farms with the necessity to prioritise the navigation safety over other uses of the sea.
- Furthermore, the Porth Authority underlined how the number of planned projects for Offshore Wind Farms is too high to be able to coexist with the current navigation routes.
- The Porth Authority suggested to reserve channels inside the Farms for navigation routes, an option that could be also considered for some types of fishing.
- Regarding the impacts on local economic activities, such as aquaculture and trawling, the industry representatives have taken the floor with the following inputs. As regards the interference of FOWTs with aquaculture, it was highlighted that, in Norway, there are already experimental projects that are verifying their coexistence. For trawling, however, the problem is much more complex and must absolutely be addressed with mitigation measures and forecasting studies.
- AERO highlighted three further critical issues:
 - The topic of the FER 2 (Renewable Energy Sources) decree, which must support an extraordinary effort in terms of incentives.
 - The opportunity provided by the MASE call to identify two or more strategic ports, for which public resources will be needed for the development of the supply chain, prefiguring extraordinary powers for ports, commissioners or other bodies to speed up the work.
 - The issue of the former ILVA plant for steeling production in Taranto: the site must be relaunched by 2024, otherwise from 2025 onwards the steel will be booked elsewhere.
- The point of view of the fishermen's cooperatives expressed the need for compensatory measures for the impact on fishing, because wind power is in contrast with this activity:

therefore, it will be necessary to establish adequate tables between the Ministries and the various fishermen's associations .

- Furthermore, there is a need to investigate whether small-scale fishing can coexist with new anchoring technologies, which are less invasive (tips, which are also used in aquaculture).

4 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

Compared to the previous MENTIMETER survey, administered to the audience of the first Italian co-creation workshop held in Bari in 2023, some specific questions had been added, regarding the active involvement of civil society and the other uses of the sea to be taken into greater consideration regarding the impacts of FOWTs, in particular regarding potentially conflicting socio-economic activities. In fact, the addition was made to take into consideration the foreseen participation of associations of fishermen and of environmental protection activists. Nevertheless, eventually, the MENTIMETER survey, scheduled on the agenda as an ice-breaker for the round table, was not administered, since the audience already engaged the speakers and the MARINEWIND experts in a discussion following each intervention, thus covering all the discussion points provided by the questions. Therefore, administering the survey would have been a redundant and superfluous action, which would have taken away useful time for further questions and issues.

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The second of the three co-creation workshops for T1.3 with regards to the Italian Lab has been mainly dedicated to keep collecting barriers perceived by the stakeholders for the investment on FOWTs, and to enablers and potential solutions. This time, the focus was mainly on the MSP for the Mediterranean Sea, with particular attention to the Lazio Region, and to the analysis of the environmental and socio-economic impacts (especially on fishing, aquaculture and tourism). The data collected regarding the barriers were systematise together with the possible solutions already emerged from the co-creation part of the workshop, as summarised in the table below.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS & SOLUTIONS
According to fishing associations, wind power is in contrast with their activity, in particular for trawling (estimated reduction of fishing areas of 43% in the Mediterranean).	<p>It will be necessary to establish adequate tables between the Ministries and the various fishermen's associations, in order to prepare proper forecasting studies and to co-design compensatory measures for the impact of FOWTs on fishing.</p> <p>Need to investigate whether small-scale fishing can coexist with new anchoring technologies, which are less invasive (tips, which are also used in aquaculture).</p>
FOWTs could affect aquaculture, too.	Need to further analyse the path traced by Norway, where there are already experimental projects that are verifying the coexistence of FOWT and aquaculture.

FOWT could damage the landscape integrity, and therefore the communities quality of life and the tourism.		Private studies have shown how Offshore Wind Farms are almost invisible on the horizon line.
According to the Port Authority, FOWT endangers the security of navigation.	The number of planned projects for Offshore Wind Farms is too high to be able to coexist with the current navigation routes.	National and international regulations, mitigation measures and forecasting studies to guarantee security for navigation.
		To encourage industry to further analyse new advanced technologies, e.g. to study the possibility of sharing mooring points.
		The Porth Authority suggested to reserve channels inside the Farms for navigation routes, an option that could be also considered for some types of fishing.
Policy framework uncertainty due to the yet unpublished MSP.		To work in synergy with the private technical developers, who have already carried out geophysical and geotechnical analyses, as per the Irish best practice on the topic: the Irish Government, while still working on their national MSP, is favouring a decentralised parallel approach, in order to shorten waiting times.
According to the regional representatives, the MSP will impact the autonomy of regional policies.	On the other hand, the industry is worried that the Suitable Areas Decree might allow the Regions to interfere with the MSP, and with the energetic exclusive competence of the State.	To have an Italian MSP as soon as possible, since the Maritime Space Planning is fundamental to reassuring investors, planning infrastructures and avoiding conflicts of perceived conflicting competences (also clarifying the difference with the Suitable Areas Decree, which is not supposed to regard offshore wind power, but only onshore).
Bringing the analysis of seabed for floating offshore to an adequate level would require funding in the order of billions of euros, so it is unlikely that the investigation will actually be addressed.		The geotechnical suitability of the seabed for anchoring should not be a prerequisite for the granting of authorisations for offshore wind farms.
The industry is concerned with the fact that the Regions might go against environmental and economic common sense when allowing the passage of electrical cables in the sea area within the territorial limit, forcing the industry to contemplate convoluted trajectories for electrical cables, slowing down the process and greatly increasing production costs.		A collaborative approach from the Regions in dealing with the electrical cables routes within the 12 miles threshold is suggested.

<p>The Ministry of Transport had not identified specific areas and bands suitable for the construction of offshore wind farm projects, so the SEA Commission has had to carry out an incomplete analysis, without including offshore. Now, the MIT has now resumed its work on the matter, and, within a year, it is supposed to be able to propose the final scenario once again. In the hypothesis that the authorisation requests already proposed do not fall within the suitable areas, the situation would open up a legal dispute with the Italian State.</p>	<p>In order to avoid a major dispute between the investments already made by the operators and the choices of the State, a safeguard clause is absolutely needed in the Suitable Areas Decree for the interventions already carried out (up to the request for a single authorisation procedure).</p>
<p>Lack of public resources needed for the development of the supply chain.</p>	<p>The FER 2 decree must correspond an adequate effort in terms of incentives.</p>
<p>The objectives for climate neutrality are too ambitious, especially if Italy chooses to focus only on a singular green technology.</p>	<p>FOWT is particularly adequate to work in synergy with other RES (e.g., photovoltaic), contributing to Italy's energy mix by 2050.</p>
<p>The general perception is that the Italian supply chain is not yet ready to meet the requests of new Wind Farms.</p>	<p>To define a clear long-term industrial vision with an ambitious objective for floating offshore wind, stimulating the development of dedicated supply chains.</p> <p>To prefigure extraordinary powers for ports, commissioners or other bodies to speed up the work.</p> <p>To promote the planning for advancing the grid in a synergistic way with the MSP</p>
<p>The general perception is that the development of renewable energy sources does not allow the creation of value directly in local territories and benefits foreign supply chains.</p>	<p>To involve not only large manufacturing companies, but also national and local SMEs, to produce positive externalities on the communities.</p> <p>To relaunch the former ILVA plant for steeling production in Taranto.</p>
<p>NIMBY protests and general opposition by the civil society.</p>	<p>To follow best practices at European level that show that there are concertation mechanisms that make stakeholder participation possible already in the definition phase of offshore wind projects, increasing their social acceptability in less than a year.</p>
<p>Even if the most severe environmental impacts (e.g., degradation of seabed, climate interferences) are currently regarded as irrelevant extreme cases (not applicable to the Mediterranean), it is important to consider the cumulative impact provoked by all the future farms together.</p>	<p>To safeguard the integrity of seabed, the world of offshore wind has already discarded the hypothesis of chaining, orienting itself instead on fixed anchoring, a technology now consolidated in the sector.</p> <p>Private experts have studied that, in the Mediterranean Sea, the temperatures are not as such as to create condensation and consequentially impacting on fog density.</p>

	<p>Concerning the modification of the wave flow, the industry-related studies have proven that the pieces of the wind farms are crossed by the wave flow in an almost transparent way.</p>
	<p>For Italy to follow the direction already taken by Spain, where they are opening six factories for the recycling of blades.</p>
	<p>To keep working on the use of a particular recyclable resin (in Europe), and to bring it to Italy, too. In general, to support the use of recyclable construction materials for wind farms.</p>
	<p>The implementation of FOWTs in the Mediterranean could bring to the creation of an artificial reef: mooring anchors and underwater cables can act as artificial coral reefs, attracting marine life and serving as valuable tools of conservation. These "barrier effects" could increase the abundance of local species, create marine refuges and generate spillover effects, increasing biodiversity.</p>
	<p>The implementation of FOWTs in the Mediterranean could bring to the emergence of new marine protected areas (with effects on the fish fauna reserve): the reduction or absence of fishing around offshore wind farms creates reserves for the species.</p>
<p>A common misconception is that there is no development potential for the FOWT Italian market.</p>	<p>Italy is the ideal country for floating offshore wind power, being the third potential market in the world. In fact, more than 60% of the Italian renewable electricity potential comes from this technology.</p>